

Effect of fungicides on BPH hatching, mortality, and percentage of *M. anisopliae* infection. For each test vertical bars sharing a common letter are not significantly different using Duncan's multiple range test.

insects and plants were sprayed with 2 ml of 0.10% benomyl or edifenphos. Living insects in each cage were recorded 1 d after the last fungicide application.

In the third test, we studied the effect of the fungicides on *M. anisopliae*. Infected BPH adults which were covered with whitish to greenish spores of the fungus were collected in the greenhouse and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish. Each dish was sprayed with 1 ml of 0.10% benomyl, edifenphos, or water. Twenty-four hours after treatment, the BPH with fungus spores were placed in a flask and thoroughly mixed with 20 cc distilled water containing 0.05% detergent. The spore solutions were sprayed on 20 of 2d- and 3d-instar BPH nymphs caged on 35-d-old potted

plants enclosed with a mylar cage. Each potted plant was sprayed with 2 ml of the solution. Seven days after spraying, the number of live BPH/cage was recorded. Treatments in each of the three tests were replicated four times.

Benomyl had no adverse effect on hatching, but edifenphos reduced hatching 34% below that with water (see figure). Benomyl was safe to BPH nymphs, producing mortality similar to that of water. Edifenphos caused 100% mortality. When nymphs were sprayed with the spore suspension, percentage of fungus-infected BPH was reduced from 33% in the control to 16% in the benomyl treatment. We are now using benomyl to control *M. anisopliae* in the BPH rearing program in wet season. □

Comparative observations of rice insect populations on indica and japonica rices

T. Fujimura, Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, 305 Japan; and P. H. Somasundaram, Entomology Division, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Gannoruwa, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka

We studied insect pest and predator population dynamics on indica and japonica rices in 1976-77 maha at Tismada, Sri Lanka, in pesticide-free fields. Two 10 × 2-m fields were transplanted on the same day, one with H-9 (indica) and one with Koshihikari (japonica). Both varieties are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Koshihikari is moderately resistant to stem borer (SB) *Chilo suppressalis*.

Insects were collected twice weekly until harvest by making 30 sweeps with a 36-cm butterfly net across the 2 fields. In the laboratory, specimens were killed, separated, and counted.

BPH, grasshopper, and *Leptispa pygmaea* populations did not differ. *Sogatella furcifera* was more abundant on the indica at early growth, but populations equalized at later stages. The GLH population was similar at

Comparative population fluctuation of two insect pests (*Nephotettix virescens* and *Leptocoris oratorius*) on two types (indica and japonica) of rice varieties.

early growth, but after heading was 10 times greater on the japonica (see figure). Cicadella spectra population was similar to that of GLH, being five times greater on the japonica after heading. There were few *Recilia dorsalis* on either variety, and slightly more *Thaia subrufa* on the indica at all stages. The *Leptocoris oratorius* population was highest and lasted longest on the japonica because it headed early. The indica had a tenfold larger population of the predator *Ophiomea indica*. □

Crop loss in deepwater rice caused by yellow stem borer (YSB)

B. Taylor and Z. Islam, ODA-BRRI Deepwater Rice Project, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

We studied YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* infestation and control in deepwater rice in 1982. In mid-Aug, when there were many moths, we sprayed monocrotophos 250 g ai/ha from a boat. YSB infestation was significantly reduced (see table).

Harvest data from two fields showed spraying increased yield 7.3 and 10% over the control.

More than 25,000 stems were dissected to determine the correlation between YSB infested stems at harvest and yield. Mean infestation was 27 to 60%, but no consistently significant correlations were found, perhaps because the stems dissected were less than 1% of the field population or because a younger crop is more sensitive to YSB damage (sampling was done at harvest).

We recorded and analyzed YSB infestation and grain sterility of the stems taken at harvest. Varieties differed in the internode most sensitive to damage. In variety Chamara despite 90% infestation (n = 254), grain loss was not significant unless the top internode was infested. In variety Sada Pankaish at lower infestation

Effect of monocrotophos (250g ai/ha) spray on YSB in deepwater rice. Dubail (Tangail) and DND Project area, Dhaka, 1982.^a

Variety	Whitehead (%)		Infested stem (%)	
	Unsprayed	Sprayed	Unsprayed	Sprayed
Dubail				
Sonna digha	8.6	8.6 ns	74.6	50.5**
Chamara	5.9	2.1 **	58.0	28.2**
Boron Bawalia	10.8	2.4 **	54.0	21.0**
Sonna digha	8.2	6.1 ns	48.0	33.3*
Boron Bawalia	11.0	3.5 **	63.0	38.0**
DND				
Khama	10.3	4.7 **	57.0	45.0 ns
Khama	12.7	4.6 **	52.8	32.0**
Khama	11.8	6.3 **	70.0	59.1 ns

^aThe difference between sprayed and unsprayed areas, compared by t-test, are indicated as ns = not significant, * = significant at 5% level, and ** = significant at 1% level.

levels (37%, n = 254), infestation in either the 1st, 3d, or 4th top internodes could significantly reduce grain filling. But in both varieties, whiteheads in the top internode caused greatest yield loss.

This result was verified in another

study where varieties Chamara and Boron Bawalia showed that 94% of stems with whiteheads were infested in the top internode (n = 205) but few whiteheads were associated with infestation at the lower internodes (down to the 6th internode). □

Rice gall midge (GM) (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason) biotypes in Guangdong Province

Kor-chow Lai, Yu-juan Tan, and Ying Pan, Plant Protection Research Institute, Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, China

GM is one of the most serious pests in South China. It is found in the mountain region, in some hilly areas, and in the central plains of Guangdong Province. Biotype studies were made in 1979-83

Adults are collected from the overwintering generation that infests the wild host plant *Leersia hexandra* and

from infested rice at different sites. Damaged plants are put in pots in cages for symptom development. Adult insects are collected from the damaged plants and used to infest differential varieties.

To test for different biotypes we used Leaug 152, OB677, IET2911, W1263, Ptb21, and Muey Nahng 62M from IRRI. They were tested in 16 representative

Reactions of differential rice varieties to GM biotypes at various sites in Guangdong Province, China.

Location	Category ^a	China GM biotype	Differential reaction ^b to GM						
			Leaug 152	OB677	IET2911	W1263	Ptb21	Muey Nahng 62M	
Guangzhou region	Huaxian	H	I	MR	MR	MR	MR	S	S
	Songhua	M	I	R	MR	R	MR	S	-
	Pengyu	P	II	R	R	R	S	S	S
Fozan region	Nanhai	P	II	R	R	R	S	S	S
	Xinhui	H	II	R	R	R	S	S	-
	Sanshui	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	-
	Zhongzan	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	-
Zantou region	Chaoan	P	II	R	MR	R	S	S	S
Huiyang region	Huizhou	H	II	R	MR	MR	S	S	S
	Dongwan	P	I	R	R	R	MR	S	S
Shaoguan region	Shaoguan	M	I	R	R	R	R	S	S
	Lianshan	M	III	S	S	S	R	S	S
Meixian region	Meixian	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S
	Wuhua	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	-
Shaoqing region	Fenkai	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S
Zhanjiang region	Xinyi	M	IV	S	S	S	S	S	S

^a H = hilly area, M = mountain region, P = plain. ^b MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible.